

Phase Difference During Propagation of a Wave at a Given Instance on its Path

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Abstract: Propagation of light waves at a constant speed c with respect to all reference frames that are in relative uniform movement with respect to each other is the accepted principle of physics in the modern era. This leads to the principle of the relativity of simultaneity, the space-time continuum and the block universe that means the existence of past, present and future in a four-dimensional space-time continuum. The principle of relativity of simultaneity essentially means that the tenses, past present and future, are a illusion. Time order of events are subjective and thus all events in the universe exist together on the continuum. The origin of these concepts are generally accepted as validated by the Michelson and Morley experiment and similar experiments repeated in later years. In this work we show that the phase difference at a given instance in the propagation of a light wave does not depend upon the apparent or real calibration differences of rulers and clocks. The amplitude of the wave at a given space-time point is external to the calibration issues and thus will not be affected by apparent or actual contraction of the rulers and/or changes in clock ticks. The interference pattern of two waves that are the merging of the phase differences of these two waves at a given instance is independent of the spatial and time coordinates assigned by different measurement systems. We show that the interference pattern remains unaltered under the three transformations. Galilean, Tangherlinian and Lorentz, and in fact in any linear transformation of the space-time coordinates. We conclude that the Michelson Morley experiment and such other experiments do not validate or invalidate any of the three transformations. Students will appreciate that calibration (of rulers and clocks) and synchronization (of distant clocks) issues can alter perception of speed and linear measurements but cannot change the observation about events, in this case the interference pattern that is the superposition of two waves.

1.0 Introduction:

Propagation of light waves at a constant speed c with respect to all reference frames that are in relative uniform movement with respect to each other is the accepted principle of physics in the modern era. This leads to the principle of the relativity of simultaneity, the space-time continuum and the block universe that means the existence of past, present and future in a four-dimensional space-time continuum. The principle of relativity of simultaneity essentially means that the tenses, past present and future, are a illusion. Time order of events are subjective and thus all events in the universe exist together on the continuum, also known as the 'Block Universe' [1].

The origin of these concepts are generally accepted as validated by the Michelson and Morley experiment and similar experiments repeated in later years.

The awareness of the flow of time is related to human consciousness and the relationship between physical processes both internal and external to the human body. However, temporal order or time order does not measure duration but only the before, after or simultaneous nature of two events, and does not require the measurement of the magnitude of the time interval. It has been suggested that even if between two events A and B, if we are unable to recall or specify the amount of elapsed time, whether A happened before B or otherwise cannot be altered [2]

A detailed discussion on the experimental proofs of relativistic length contraction and their possible alternative interpretations is given in [3]

The reality or apparentness of the contraction of a moving rod is discussed, scientifically and historically, in detail in [4].

Assignment of a number to a spatial location from a chosen origin is a subjective matter in that it could be for example in feet or meters. Suppose we use a meter ruler and if the meter ruler contracts (say for example in the winter) and we use the ruler without being aware that the ruler has contracted, we may assign slightly different numbers to locations in space. However, this will not alter the basic structure of the universe. Events such as meeting of two persons or collision of two objects remain essentially unaffected in their characteristics by the assigned numbers to the spatial and temporal perspective by different systems of measurement.

The phase difference of two interfering waves depends only on the amplitudes of the interfering waves. Spatial and time coordinates assigned to the location of the interference pattern will not alter the interference pattern. We show in the following sections, while different systems may alter the perception of wavelength, frequency and speed of propagation (in a given reference frame), the amplitudes and hence the interference pattern will remain unaltered. Here by different measurement systems, we mean two different systems adopted to measure lengths and time within a reference frame. That means there is no movement involved between the two systems. They both measure lengths and time in the same reference frame.

2.0 Phase difference under Lorentz and Galilean dispensations.

An instant of a wave front with maximum amplitude leaves the origin at $t = 0$, in the reference frame comoving with the source (K). Event 1, at $(x=0, t=0)$

This wave front reaches the location (ct, t) in reference frame K.(Event 2), propagating at the speed c , the speed of light in vacuum.

The phase difference is Nil between events 1 and 2 as the propagation equation

$$\text{Amplitude} = A_{\max} \sin 2\pi \left\{ \left(\frac{x}{\lambda} \right) - \omega t \right\}$$

With $\omega = c/\lambda$ and $x = ct$, the expression $(x/\lambda) - \omega t = 0$ and as expected the same instant of the wave propagating at c , retains its phase between events 1 $(0,0)$ and event 2 (ct,t) .

2.1 Transformation by Lorentz

When we transform events 1, 2 from the frame K to another reference frame K'; moving at v along the x axis, when we assume that the Lorentz transformation is the correct one, we get for a receding wave from any standard text,

$$\text{New wave length in K}' = \lambda \frac{\left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)^{1/2}}{\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)^{1/2}} = \lambda_L$$

$$\text{New frequency in K}' = \omega \frac{\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)^{1/2}}{\left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)^{1/2}} = \omega_L$$

The product of the above two remains c, the propagation speed as stipulated by the synchronization convention maintaining the speed of light as c in K' as well. The subscript L indicates that these are in the moving frame K', using the Lorentz Transformation between K to K'.

The two events (0,0) and (ct,t) in K transform in K' by Lorentz to

$$(0,0) \text{ and } (ct-vt)\gamma, (t-v(ct)/c^2)\gamma, \text{ where } \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

$$\text{Phase difference} = \{ (x'/\lambda_L) - \omega_L t' \} = ((ct-vt)\gamma / \lambda_L) - \omega_L (t-v(ct)/c^2)\gamma$$

Noting that $\omega_L = c/\lambda_L$ as per the Einstein synchronization convention, this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Phase Difference} &= \left(\frac{\gamma}{\lambda_L}\right) [(ct-vt) - c (t-v(ct)/c^2)] \\ &= \left(\frac{\gamma}{\lambda_L}\right) [(ct-vt) - (ct-vt)] \end{aligned}$$

we see that the above expression becomes zero. Thus the phase difference between events 1 & 2 is zero in K' also (as in K).

2.2 Transformation by Galilean equations

In Galilean method, In K' event 2 coordinates transform to { (ct-vt), t }

The wavelength remains the same as λ as the instant remains unchanged between K and K' in the Galilean dispensation. There is no contraction of rulers (apparent or real), thus the distance between two peaks of the wave remain same in K and K'.

$$\text{Thus } \lambda_G = \lambda$$

The speed of propagation is (c-v) in Galilean and thus the frequency becomes (c-v)/ λ = ω_G

Thus we have phase difference = $(x'/\lambda) - \{(c-v)/\lambda\}t'$

Noting $t' = t$ in Galilean and $x' = ct - vt$, we get the phase difference to be zero in the Galilean method also.

2.3 Summary

Thus we see while the Galilean transformation altered the frequency and speed of propagation and did not alter the wavelength, the Lorentz transformation altered the wavelength and frequency and did not alter the speed of propagation. But the phase of the wave front was retained at the location (x,t) when transformed either by Lorentz or Galilean dispensations.

3.0 Transformation from isotropic frame by Tangherlini Transformation.

The Tangherlini Transformation is well known to maintain the round trip speed of light as constant and maintain the same synchronization as the isotropic frame. The resultant coordinates lead to an anisotropic frame with onward propagation speed as $c/(1+(v/c))$ and the return propagation speed as $c/(1-(v/c))$ with the average round trip speed, that is the harmonic mean of the onward and return speeds as c .

The Tangherlini Transformation from isotropic frame to another (anisotropic) frame with the round trip speed of light as constant is given by

$$x' = (x-vt)\gamma$$

$$t' = t/\gamma$$

The speed of propagation in the onward path is $(ct-vt)\gamma / (t/\gamma) = c/(1+(v/c))$

In the return path the speed of propagation is $c/(1-(v/c))$

On the onward path, two peaks at $(0,0)$ & $(\lambda,0)$ in the isotropic frame K will be observed at $(0,0)$ & $(\gamma\lambda,0)$ by substituting $x=0$ & $x=\lambda$ and $t=0$ in the above equations. Thus the observed wave length is $\lambda' = \gamma\lambda$.

Observed frequency = speed of propagation/ wavelength $\omega' = c/\{(1+(v/c))\gamma\lambda\}$

For any point x,t in the isotropic frame, the phase difference is

$$(x/\lambda) - \omega t = (x-ct)/\lambda \text{ since } \omega, \text{ the frequency is } c/\lambda.$$

The same is translated by the Tangherlini transformations to

$$(x'/\lambda') - \omega' t' = (x-vt)\gamma/\gamma\lambda - c(t/\gamma)/\{(1+(v/c))\gamma\lambda\}$$

This when simplified by noting that $\gamma = 1/(1-v^2/c^2)^{1/2}$ gives the same phase difference as in the isotropic frame, that is $(x-ct)/\lambda$

Thus we find that the phase difference observed at any space – time point remains same under Lorentz, Tangherlini and Galilean Transformations.

4.0 Arbitrary point (x,t) on the propagation path

4.1 Phase difference at (x,t)

Take any arbitrary point on a light wave's propagation path (x, t)

The equation of the light wave propagation is

Amplitude $A(x,t) = A_0 \sin 2\pi[(x/\lambda) - \omega t]$, where $\omega = \text{propagation speed/wave length}$.

For the isotropic frame propagation speed = c, and therefore

$$\text{Amplitude } A(x,t) = A_0 \sin 2\pi[(x/\lambda) - (c/\lambda)t] = A_0 \sin 2\pi[(x-ct)/\lambda] \text{ ----- (1)}$$

4.2 Transformation by Galilean System

(x,t) goes to $x' = (x-vt)$, $t' = t$

$$\text{Amplitude } A(x,t) = A_0 \sin 2\pi[((x-vt)/\lambda') - \omega't]$$

In this case wavelength remains same ($\lambda' = \lambda$) and speed of propagation is (c-v) for the receding wave. Frequency = propagation speed/wavelength = (c-v)/ λ . t remains unaltered in Galilean Transformation.

$$\text{Therefore Amplitude } A(x,t) = A_0 \sin 2\pi[((x-vt)/\lambda) - \omega't]$$

= $A_0 \sin 2\pi[((x-vt)/\lambda) - (c-v)t/\lambda]$ after cancelling vt/λ we get the phase difference as same as equation (1) above.

4.3 Transformation by Lorentz.

Here due to Doppler effect λ becomes $\lambda' = \lambda[(1+\beta)(1-\beta)]^{1/2}$ where $\beta = (v/c)$.

Propagation speed remains c

After transforming (x,t) to $(x-vt)\gamma$, $(t-vx/c^2)\gamma$

We find

$$\text{Amplitude} = A_0 \sin 2\pi [\{(x-vt)\gamma/\lambda'\} - (c/\lambda')\{(t-vx/c^2)\gamma\}]$$

Substituting for λ' as $\lambda[(1+\beta)/(1-\beta)]^{1/2}$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Amplitude} &= A_0 \sin 2\pi \left\{ [x(1+(v/c))\gamma/\{\lambda[(1+\beta)/(1-\beta)]^{1/2}\}] - (ct/\lambda) (1+(v/c))\gamma/ [(1+\beta)/(1-\beta)]^{1/2} \right\} \\ &= A_0 \sin 2\pi[(x-ct)/\lambda], \text{ after algebraic simplifications - same as equation (1)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the phase difference remains unaltered in all the three cases for the point (x,t), original, transformed by Galilean or Lorentz.

5.0 General Transformation of event coordinates within a inertial frame

A General linear transformation of event coordinates is

$$X = ax + bt$$

$$T = px + qt$$

X may be rewritten as $a\{x - (bt/a)\}$

thus whenever $X = 0$, $x = bt/a$, making the origin of K' move at a speed of (b/a)

Thus if we require a general transformation that has zero relative speeds, that is within a reference frame, then it becomes

$$X = ax$$

$$T = px + qt$$

We can call the (x,t) coordinates as A and the (X,T) coordinates as B, (instead of using K and K') emphasising that there is no movement between the system of coordinates A and B. But there is relativity of simultaneity between A and B when p is not equal to zero.

Let us assume that in the coordinate system A, light waves are propagating at speed c with wave length λ and frequency ω , such that $\lambda \omega = c$

Let us consider a peak that leaves from $(0,0)$ and another peak that is at $(\lambda,0)$ in coordinate system A. The peak at $(\lambda,0)$ is propagating with coordinates

$$(\lambda + \Delta x, \Delta x/c)$$

When transformed to coordinate system B, this propagation is transformed to

$\Lambda = a(\lambda + \Delta x)$ and $0 = p(\lambda + \Delta x) + (q/c) \Delta x$ as we require the distance between two peaks at the same instant in coordinate system B, for determining Λ , the wave length in coordinate system B.

From $p(\lambda + \Delta x) + (q/c) \Delta x = 0$, we get $\Delta x = -p \lambda / (p + (q/c))$

And therefore $\Lambda = a \lambda \{1 - (p/(p + (q/c)))\} = (a \lambda q/c) / (p + (q/c))$

When $p = 0$, the synchronization shift is absent and $\Lambda = a \lambda$

In general $\Lambda = (a \lambda q/c) / (p + (q/c))$

Speed of propagation in coordinate system B will be

(ct, t) in A goes to $(act, (pct + qt))$ in B

Thus the speed of propagation in B = $ac/(pc + q)$

Frequency in B = speed/ wavelength = $ac/(pc + q) / \Lambda$

= $ac/(pc + q) / \{ (a \lambda q/c) / (p + (q/c)) \}$

$$= (c/\lambda q)$$

$$= \omega/q$$

Therefore the frequency observed by coordinate system B is frequency observed by coordinate system A divided by q.

$$\text{That is } \Omega = \omega/q$$

It is also noted that the inverse of the system

$$X = ax$$

$$T = px + qt$$

is

$$x = (X/a)$$

$$t = -pX/aq + T/q$$

Phase difference observed by the systems A and B

With the standard wave propagation equation the phase of the wave at (x,t) in the coordinate system A is $(x/\lambda) - \omega t$

When c is the propagation speed as determined by A, this becomes

$$\text{Phase difference (between location (0,0) and (x,t))} = (x-ct)/\lambda$$

When transformed to coordinate system B,

$$\text{It becomes } (X/\Lambda) - \Omega T$$

$$= (ax/\Lambda) - (\omega/q)(px+qt)$$

$$\text{Substituting for } \Lambda \text{ as } (a \lambda q/c) / (p+(q/c))$$

$$\text{Phase difference} = (ax / \{(a \lambda q/c) / (p+(q/c))\}) - (\omega/q)(px+qt)$$

Simplifying and noting that $\omega = (c/\lambda)$ we get

$$\text{Phase difference} = (x-ct)/\lambda \text{ as observed by coordinate system B also.}$$

Thus the phase difference observed by both the coordinate systems A and B is identical and equal to $(x-ct)/\lambda$

In other words calibration differences in rulers and clocks & distant synchronization differences (relativity of simultaneity) leave the observed phase

difference unaltered when a inertial reference frame is using two coordinate systems A and B with no relative motion between A and B.

It may also be noted that the alternate pathways for the decomposition of the Lorentz transformation have been discussed in [5] in matrix notation. We shall be following a similar matrix approach in the next section to reiterate the conclusions derived so far.

6.0 Transformation between Galilean to Lorentz as a single matrix within K'

Suppose we have a choice in reference frame K' to transform event coordinates of K by Galilean or Lorentz, these two choices can be transformed into one another by a single matrix as detailed below.

The left most transformation in the below equation transforms a Lorentz transformation (LT) to Galilean.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1/\gamma & 0 \\ v\gamma/c^2 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -v\gamma \\ -v\gamma/c^2 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -v \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

In the same way the left most transformation in the below equation transforms a Galilean transformation to Lorentz.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma & 0 \\ -v\gamma/c^2 & 1/\gamma \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -v \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & -v\gamma \\ -v\gamma/c^2 & \gamma \end{pmatrix}$$

And

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1/\gamma & 0 \\ v\gamma/c^2 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & 0 \\ -v\gamma/c^2 & 1/\gamma \end{pmatrix} = I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The two matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1/\gamma & 0 \\ v\gamma/c^2 & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \begin{pmatrix} \gamma & 0 \\ -v\gamma/c^2 & 1/\gamma \end{pmatrix}$$

Do not result in any movement. They are assigning only different numbers to spatial and time measurements **in the same inertial reference frame**. They will not change the here and now magnitudes of

the interfering amplitudes of two waves. These two matrices conform to the analysis given in the previous section 5 in that there is zero relative speed in both these matrices. With regard to the asynchronisation element p , as mentioned in section 5, this may be viewed in the context of the importance of correct synchronisation in observing event coordinates as emphasized in [6].

Extending the same concept to three-dimensional space with a time metric, one can state that within a inertial reference frame, if two sets of observers follow two different measurement systems, the transformation between the two systems, in the most general case, will be of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 \\ a_{41} & a_{42} & a_{43} & a_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ t \end{pmatrix}$$

The three zeros appearing in the last column specify that there is no movement between the two measuring systems. There are only calibration differences and temporal asynchronisation in the spatial directions as indicated by the elements a_{41} , a_{42} and a_{43} in the three spatial directions. It is easy to deduce that such a transformation will not alter the phase of a propagating wave when it reaches a spatial location, even though the two systems may assign different spatial and temporal coordinates to that spatial location. Evidently, the inverse of above 4x4 transformation will be of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ t \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{13} & 0 \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & b_{23} & 0 \\ b_{31} & b_{32} & b_{33} & 0 \\ b_{41} & b_{42} & b_{43} & a_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ T \end{pmatrix}$$

Once again indicating that there is no movement or velocity between the two measurement systems. When the three spatial coordinate axis of measurement systems A and B are aligned (collinear), the non-diagonal elements of the first three rows will be zero. The non-diagonal elements of the fourth row a_{41} , a_{42} , a_{43} , b_{41} , b_{42} , and b_{43} refer to temporal asynchronization along the three spatial axis. The diagonal elements refer to the calibration scale differences along the three spatial and one temporal axis. Although the two sets of observers may differ in the spatial coordinates and temporal recordings of a given event, the characteristics of the event will be identical as observed by the two sets of observers. One following the x,y,z,t system and the other following the X,Y,Z,T system with no movement as indicated by the three zeros in the last column of the above two matrices. For example let

x, y, z, t be the measurement system (A) in K' transformed by a Galilean transformation from a reference frame K , that is in uniform motion with respect to reference frame K' , and let X, Y, Z, T be the measurement system (B) in K' , transformed by a Lorentz transformation from K . Thus we have two measurement systems A and B in K' . The coordinates of any event may differ in systems A and B, but the characteristics of the observation about the event will not differ.

Students will appreciate that calibration (of rulers and clocks) and synchronization (of distant clocks) issues can alter perception of speed and linear measurements but cannot change the observation about events, in this case the interference pattern that is the superposition of two waves.

7.0 Conclusion

The transformations Lorentz, Galilean and Tangherlini differ in the scale of spatial and temporal measurements and distant clock synchronization convention. The amplitude of the interfering waves are external to these assignments of spatial and temporal coordinates. Although wavelength, frequency and speed of propagation may differ under these three transformations, the interference pattern remains unaltered. Only the spatial and temporal numbers assigned to the location of the screen on which the interference occurs differ. The pattern itself is unaltered. Thus the M&M and other such experiments do not validate or invalidate any one of the three transformations namely, Galilean, Lorentz or Tangherlini.

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